

A Study of Mental Health and Self-Concept of Secondary School Students

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Received : 02/08/2023

1st BPR : 09/08/2023

2nd BPR : 20/08/2023

Accepted : 29/08/2023

Abstract

Diagnosis of mental health has become increasingly reified. People are being labelled; they are seen as being mentally ill instead of having a mental illness. Unfortunately, negative stereotypes are associated with mental illness. According to labelling theory, the stigma of being labelled mentally ill actually causes one to be mentally ill as a result of effects described as self-fulfilling prophecy. According to a modified version of the theory, assumptions about causation are omitted, and only the negative impact on self-concept is addressed. This impact is described in later research about stigma and self-stigma. Stigma can have negative consequences for self-concept by lowering self-efficacy, which fosters dysfunctional coping styles and ultimately reduces quality of self-concept. Also, stigma can be internalized and create self-stigma, in which the label predominates self-concept and reduces self-esteem. Thus, eventually, the reification of diagnosis leads to lowered self-concept through stigmatization effects. In spite of these negative effects, it is reasonable to believe that positive effects also exist. A label could foster self-acceptance, causing one to seek treatment, and can also foster interpersonal understanding. It is argued that these effects should be investigated. On the basis of outcomes, it should be decided whether diagnosis should or should not be reported to the patient.

Keywords: Mental Health, Self-Concept.

INTRODUCTION

The thing which is mostly desired in all the societies of the world is the need of preserving mental health of the individual. **Mental health** is a potent determinant of one's integrated personality and balanced behaviour identified on the basis of the level of his/her adjustment to own self, others and environment. The acquisition of such personality is indeed essential for a normal individual. Only then, an individual can be able to actualize him/her, live his/her life to his/her satisfaction in the perfect tune of talking and giving something to the society. Mental health is a state of well-being in which a person understands his or her own abilities, can cope with the normal stresses of life, can work productively and fruitfully, and is able to make a contribution to his or her community. Both physical and mental health are the result of a complex interplay between many individual and environmental factors, including: family history of illness and disease/genetics lifestyle and health behaviors (e.g., smoking, exercise, substance use) levels of personal and workplace stress exposure to toxin sex posture to trauma personal life circumstances and history access to supports (e.g., timely healthcare, social supports) coping skills. When the demands placed on someone exceed their resources and coping abilities, their mental health will be negatively affected. Two examples of common demands are: i) working long hours under difficult circumstances, and ii) caring for a chronically ill relative or friend. Economic hardship, unemployment, underemployment and poverty also have the potential to harm mental health. Mental health determines how you think, feel and act. Good mental health is when you feel positive about yourself and cope well with the everyday pressures. If you experience issues dealing

with everyday problems, it could be a sign of a mental health problem and should be addressed immediately.

Mental health is not just a concept that refers to an individual's psychological and emotional well-being. Rather it's a state of psychological and emotional well-being where an individual is able to use their cognitive and emotional capabilities, meet the ordinary demand and functions in the society.

Self-Concept refers to the totality of a compels organized and dynamic system of learned beliefs, attitudes and opinions that each person holds to be true about his or her personal existence parental upbringing, continuous failure, depression for all motivated behavior. It is the self-concept that gives rise to possible selves, and it is possible selves that create the motivation for behavior. We develop and maintain our self-concept through the process of taking action and then reflecting on what we have done and can do in comparison to our expectations and accomplishments of others. It is true that self-concept is not innate but it can develop by individual through interaction with the environment and reflecting on the interaction. There are several different components of self-concept: physical, academic, social and transpersonal. The physical aspect of self-concept relates to that which is concrete: what we look, like our sex, height etc. what kind of clothes we wear; what kind of car we drive; what kind of home we live in; and so forth. Our academic self-concept relates to how well we do in school or how well we learn. There are two levels: A general academic self-concept i.e., how good we are overall and a set of specific content related self-concept that describe how good we are in math, science, language, arts, social science etc. Self-concept is a dominant element in personality pattern, therefore, there are several terms that are virtually synonymous with self-concept among them are "self-image" the "Ego", "self-understanding" "self-perception" and "self-phenomenal". Having reviewed a variety of positions on the nature of the self-concept, we are now in a position summarize the characteristics that others have attributed to it. These include the following: 1. It is a subsystem of internally consistent, hierarchically organized concepts contained within a broader conceptual System. 2. It contains different empirical selves, such as a body self, a Spiritual self and a social self. 3. It is a dynamic organization that changes with experience. It appears to seek out change and exhibits a tendency to assimilate increasing amounts of information, there by manifesting something like a growth principle. 4. It develops out of experience, particularly out of social interaction with significant others. 5. It is essential for the functioning of the individual that the organization of the self-concept be maintained. When the organization of the self-concept is threatened, the individual experiences anxiety and attempts to defend him against the threat. If the Defense is unsuccessful, stress mounts and is followed by ultimately by total disorganization. 6. There is a need for self-concept which relates to all aspects of the and, in comparison to which, almost all other needs are subordinate.

Various studies related to mental health and self-concept have been done previously as **Susheel K. Khetarpal, Lauren S. Auster, Elizabeth Miller, Tina R. Goldstein (2022)** [Transition age youth mental health: addressing the gap with telemedicine](#) Child Adolesc Psychiatry Ment Health. 2022; 16: 8. Published online 2022 Feb 2. doi: 10.1186/s13034-022-00444-3 **PMCID: PMC8809232**. **Anitha.j and Parmashwari.G (2013)**. Correlates of Self Concept among High School Students in Chennai City, Tamil nadu, India, International Journal of Current Research and Academic Review, VOL. 1 Nov.4 (2013) Pp. 30-34. **Kumari, Archana (2013)**. "A Study on Self Concept and Academic Achievement of Secondary School Students, Journal of Sociological Research Vol.4, No2 (2013). Here we want to find out the relationship between mental health and self-concept of secondary school students.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM: -

A Study of Mental Health and Self-Concept of Secondary School Students.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY:-

1. To study the relationship between mental health and self-concept of secondary school students.
2. To study the relationship between mental health and self-concept of male secondary school students.

- To study the relationship between mental health and self-concept of female secondary school students.

HYPOTHESES OF THE STUDY: -

- There is no significant relationship between mental health and self-concept of secondary school students.
- There is no significant relationship between mental health and self-concept of male secondary school students.
- There is no significant relationship between mental health and self-concept of female secondary school students.

DELIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY: -

- The study was delimited to Saharanpur District only.
- The study was delimited to U.P. Board schools only.
- The study was delimited to the secondary school students only.

METHODOLOGY: - Descriptive survey research method was applied in the present study.

VARIABLES: - The variables which have been used in the study are-

- Independent variable – Mental Health
- Dependent Variable – Self-Concept

TOOLS USED:-

Mental Health:-Mental Health Battery developed by Dr. AK. Singh & Dr. Alpana Sen. Gupta
Self-Concept: - self-concept inventory developed by Dr. Beena shah

SAMPLE: - By using Random sampling 120 students from secondary school, District- Saharanpur, U.P. Therefore, the present study consists of 120 secondary school students as 60 male students and 60 female students.

STATISTICAL TECHNIQUE USED: - Product Moment Correlation Coefficient method was applied for analysing the data in the study.

ANALYSIS & INTERPRETATION OF DATA: -

TABLE NO. 1

Showing Correlation coefficient of mental health and self-concept of secondary school students

GROUPS	N	r	df	Level of significance
Mental health	120	0.452	118	**Significant
Self-concept				

** Significant at both .05 & .01 levels

Table shows that the calculated value of correlation coefficient between mental health and self-concept of secondary school students 0.452 is more than the tabulated value 0.256 at 0.01 level of significant which shows a positive correlation between mental health and self-concept. Hence the null hypothesis (Ho) is rejected here which states that there is significant relationship between mental health and self-concept of secondary school students. Hence, it may be interpreted that when overall mental health of secondary school students increases, self-concept of secondary schools also increases and when overall mental health of secondary school students decreases, self-concept of secondary schools also decreases.

TABLE NO. 2

Showing Correlation coefficient of mental health and self-concept of male secondary school students

GROUPS	N	r	df	Level of significance
Mental health	60	0.429	58	**Significant
Self-concept				

** Significant at both .05 & .01 levels

Table shows that the calculated value of correlation coefficient between mental health and self-concept of male secondary school students 0.429 is more than the tabulated value 0.330 at 0.01 level of significant which shows a positive correlation between mental health and self-concept. Hence the null hypothesis (Ho) is rejected here which states that there is significant relationship between mental health and self-concept of male secondary school students. Hence, it may be interpreted that when overall mental health of male secondary school students increases, self-concept of male secondary school students also increases and when overall mental health of male secondary school students decreases, self-concept of male secondary schools also decreases.

TABLE NO. 3
Showing Correlation coefficient of mental health and self-concept of female secondary school students

GROUPS	N	r	df	Level of significance
Mental health	60	0.510	58	**Significant
Self-concept				

** Significant at both .05 & .01 levels

Table shows that the calculated value of correlation coefficient between mental health and self-concept of female secondary school students 0.510 is more than the tabulated value 0.330 at 0.01 level of significant which shows a positive correlation between mental health and self-concept. Hence the null hypothesis (Ho) is rejected here which states that there is significant relationship between mental health and self-concept of female secondary school students. Hence, it may be interpreted that when overall mental health of female secondary school students increases, self-concept of female secondary school students also increases and when overall mental health of female secondary school students decreases, self-concept of female secondary schools also decreases.

CONCLUSIONS: -

Any research study can never be called research study of education unless it does not have its educational implications. The results of the research should enhance the quality of educational system. The objective of this study was to study the mental health and self-concept of secondary school students. The findings of this study can be beneficial for our educational policy maker, psychologist & research scholar of education & psychology. This study provides knowledge about the mental health and self-concept of secondary school students with reference to gender. This study reveals that there should be a harmonious environment at school & home for the development of balanced personality otherwise student's mental health can be affected adversely. It also needs to through the interaction between social adaptation and environment, and then influence the mental health. Self-concept through a good social adaptation can provide the power and source for mental health, and poor social adaptation will lead to the hidden trouble about the more psychological problems. This study reveals that there should be good relationship between the teachers, authorities and students. This self-concept theory suggests that perceived improvement should increase both negative and positive mental health because it violates the self-consistency standard but satisfies the self-enhancement standard.

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